

SOCIOECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Production

Production potential and economics of rice-based relay cropping systems

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We experimented 1985-86 and 1986-87 with eight relay cropping systems—rice - field pea, rice - bengal gram, rice - lentil, rice - lathyrus, rice - green gram, rice - black gram, rice - linseed, and rice - coriander—in the rainfed lowlands at RRS, Keonjhar. Relay crops were broadcast in soft mud at 1.5 times normal seeding rates, 19 Nov 1985 and

Production and economics of different rice-based relay cropping systems.^a 1985-87, Orissa, India.

Cropping system	Rice grain yield (t/ha)	Rice straw yield (t/ha)	Relay crop green pod or grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Gross profit (\$/ha)	Net profit (\$/ha)
Rice - field pea	5.2	4.1	2.9	1191.31	891.61
Rice - Bengal gram	4.8	3.9	8.0+	944.38	686.72
Rice - lentil	4.7	3.7	0.4	791.02	525.99
Rice - lathyrus	4.6	3.6	0.5	784.45	529.85
Rice - linseed	4.5	3.5	0.3	688.98	451.09
Rice - coriander	4.4	3.5	0.2	756.72	506.06
Rice - green gram	4.4	3.4	F	592.04	365.99
Rice - black gram	4.5	3.5	F	604.60	378.32

^aMean of 2 yr. ^bF = failed. + = green pod.

31 Oct 1986, 15-20 d before rice harvest (dough stage). The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications.

Local improved rice variety T141 (145 d) was transplanted both years. Soil of the experimental site was clay loam, of medium fertility, with pH 6.5.

Rice - field pea was most economic, with a \$891.61/ha net profit (the field pea in this system was sold as a green pod vegetable) (see table). Two crops—green gram and black gram—failed both years because of shading, excessive initial soil moisture, and low temperature. □

Economics of N application to rice in rainfed lowland

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Field trials were conducted during dry season 1981 and 1982 to evaluate the economics of N application to rice. Tripura is situated between 22°56' and 24°32' N, 90°10' and 92°21' E. The climate is generally warm and humid, with temperatures ranging from 9 to 34 °C. Average annual rainfall is 2,100 mm. Soil is sandy loam, with pH 5.4, 0.06% total N, and 0.9% organic C.

Four levels of N (0, 40, 80, and 120 kg/ha) were applied in randomized block design, replicated three times. A uniform 17.6 kg P and 33 kg K/ha were applied as single superphosphate and muriate of potash. Two seedlings of 28-

Table 1. Rice yield under different N levels. Tripura, India, 1981 and 1982 dry season.

N level (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)		
	1981	1982	Mean
Control	1.6	2.0	1.8
40	2.6	2.5	2.6
80	3.0	2.8	2.9
120	2.0	2.6	2.3
SE ±	0.3	0.3	0.3
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.1	0.6

d-old IR36 were transplanted the second week of Feb both years. Recommended agronomic practices were followed.

N at 80 kg/ha yielded significantly higher both years (Table 1).

Response curves were fitted for individual years (see figure). The equations fit the data, as evidenced by significant coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.95 - 0.99$) and quadratic effects

Effect of N fertilization on grain yield of dry season rice IR36 on lungka land in Tripura, India.

(SE ± 0.32, 0.43), indicating that higher N would depress yield.

Expected yield for N level and the N level predicted to give the highest and

the economically optimum return were worked out as

$$(i) \text{ N level giving the maximum response } \frac{dy}{dn} = b + 2cN = 0$$

$$(ii) \text{ Economic level of } N = b P_k + 2cN P_k - P_n = 0 \text{ i.e. } \frac{1}{2c} \left(\frac{P_n}{P_k} - b \right)$$

where P, is the price of N/ kg; P_k is the price of rice/ kg; and b and c are the coefficients of linear and quadratic terms of the N response function, respectively.

The pooled analysis indicated that the N level for the highest yield was 67

kg/ ha and that for optimum profit was 47 kg/ ha (Table 2). Therefore it was recommended that for growing short-duration rice varieties, farmers should apply only 45-50 kg N/ ha under such conditions. □

Table 2. Rice grain yield and economics of N application for maximum production and most profitable level of production. Tripura, India, 1981 and 1982 dry season.

Factor	N level (kg/ha)	Cost of N (\$/ha)	Expected grain yield ^a (kg/ha)	Response yield ^b (kg/ha)	Value of response yield (\$/ha)	Net profit due to N application (\$/ha)	Net profit (\$)/\$ invested in N
<i>1981</i>							
Max physical production	66	23.76	2978	1425	142.50	118.74	4.9974
Most profitable level of production	52	18.72	2913	1360	136.00	117.28	6.2649
<i>1982</i>							
Max physical production	78	28.08	2694	662	66.20	38.12	1.3575
Most profitable level of production	44	15.84	2570	538	53.80	37.96	2.3964
<i>Pooled</i>							
Max physical production	67	24.12	2782	989	98.90	74.78	3.1003
Most profitable level of production	47	16.92	2694	901	90.10	73.18	4.3250

^aExpected yields were worked out from the equations given in the figure. ^bResponse yield = expected yield minus yield obtained at 0 level N.

ANNOUNCEMENTS

Origin of cultivated rice

No one has done more experimental work on the origin of cultivated rice than Dr. H. I. Oka. He traveled throughout Asia, Africa, Australia, and Latin America to study its wild and weedy relatives in their natural habitats. His seed collection is located at the National Institute of Genetics, Misima, Japan, where he and his students of 30 yr carried out systematic investigations on species relationships, crossability barriers, F₁ sterility, population dynamics, and ecological and genetic aspects of *Oryza*.

After his retirement, Dr. Oka lectured at universities and research institutes in Japan, China, and elsewhere. Those lectures have now been published jointly by the Japan Scientific Societies Press Tokyo and Elsevier Science Publishers, Amsterdam. The subject matter is arranged in 10 chapters: 1) The genus

Oryza, 2) The ancestors of cultivated rice, 3) Ecology and population biology of the common wild rice, 4) Genetic variation and evolutionary dynamics, 5) The dynamics of domestication, 6) The homeland of *Oryza sativa*, 7) Indica-japonica differentiation of rice cultivars, 8) Functions and genetic basis of reproductive barriers, 9) Variations in adaptability to environment, and 10) Germplasm conservation, with an extensive reference list.

Asian common wild rice, considered to be the progenitor of cultivated rice, is discussed in detail. The dynamics of domestication are considered with regard to hybridization, selection, formation of weedy types, and accumulation of genetic diversity. Recent archeological findings are cited in relation to the beginning of rice culture. Practical aspects of crop evolutionary studies concerned with breeding philosophy and germplasm

conservation are discussed briefly, and attention is drawn to environmental conservation and the need to diversify crop germplasm.

Origin of cultivated rice is distributed in Japan by Japan Scientific Societies Press, 6-2-10 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113; in the U.S.A. and Canada by Elsevier Science Publishing Company, Inc., 52 Vanderbilt Avenue, New York, NY 10017; and for the rest of the world by Elsevier Science Publishers, 25 Sara Burgerhartstraat, P.O. Box 211, 1000 AE Amsterdam, The Netherlands. □

Rice postproduction manual

Reduction of loss is one way to make more food available for consumption. Rice sustains more loss between harvest and the consumer than any other cereal.